

Effect of Assertiveness Training on Low Self Esteem Among Secondary School Students in Enugu North Local Government Area, Enugu State, Nigeria

Rev. Sr. Dr. Susana Amaka Obineli (Ph.D)¹, & Rosemary Onyinyechi Ezioko²

^{1,2}Department of Guidance and Counselling,
Faculty of Education
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831261>

Abstract

This study investigated the effect of assertiveness training on Low Self Esteem among Secondary School Students in Enugu North LGA, Enugu State. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The study made use of a pre-test, post-test approach, one experimental and one control, non-randomized non-equivalent group. The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. The population of the study comprised all the 508 pretested and identified low self esteem secondary school students through the administration of 'Hare Self Esteem Scale' (HSS), from the four coeducational schools in Enugu North L.G.A. Enugu State. Hare self esteem scale is a standardized instrument; it was used for pre-test and post-test measures. The sample of the study was made up 114 secondary school students, comprised all the low self esteem students from two co-educational schools using purposive sampling. Arithmetic mean was used to answer research questions, while Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 levels of significance was used in testing the null hypotheses. The findings of this study revealed that assertiveness training was insignificant since it had just slight effect on the experimental group over the control group, slight effect on male trained with assertiveness training over the female trained with assertiveness training, and slight effect on low self esteem junior secondary school students trained with assertiveness training over the low self esteem senior secondary school students trained with assertiveness training. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that; Counsellor Educators, professional counsellors and counsellors in training can improve their counselling techniques by attending conferences, seminars and workshops to get them grounded in areas of assertiveness training to enable them have significant impact on low self esteem secondary school students when trained with assertiveness training. Also, Counsellors should at least once in every academic session organize seminar for parents to enlighten them on how to help their children especially those with low self esteem, to have new knowledge in assertive behaviours.

Keywords: Assertiveness, self-esteem, co-education, Counsellor

Introduction

Self esteem is dependent on one's social attitudes in relating to peers and significant others such as; parents, teachers in one's life. These attitudes contribute to self esteem because, one with good social attitudes such as; confident, politeness, mutual respect is likely to build satisfying

relationships and to receive positive feedbacks from others, while one with poor social attitudes such as; abuse of drugs, prostitution, premarital sex, is likely to have unsatisfying relationships and to receive negative feedback. However, self-esteem (low or high) as a personality construct definitely affects all aspect of one's life. High self esteem people are those who really believe in themselves, have confidence, are proud of who they are and are always thinking that they are winners. According to Baker and Scarth (2002), people who feel worthy, able and competent have signs of high self esteem and they are likely to achieve their life goals. On the other hand, the low self esteem people are those who do not believe in themselves, scared of the world, afraid of trying new things and always thinking they are losers. For the purpose of this study, the researcher will dwell more on low self esteem.

In Nigeria society, some children operate at very low levels of sociability. They cannot interact freely with other children or in meaningful social contact with other peers and teachers, even their parents. Such children rarely engage in social interactions with others, and they are therefore regarded as low self esteem students. According to Barnow, Lucht, and Freyberger (2005), individuals with low self esteem have a difficult time with problems, are overtly self critical, and can become passive, withdrawn, and depressed. They may hesitate to try new things, may speak negatively about themselves, are easily frustrated, and often see temporary problems as permanent conditions. They are pessimistic about themselves and their life (Baumeister, Campell, Krueger & Vohs, 2003).

Generally, low self esteem is occasioned when one looks down on oneself and finds every negative thing about oneself to pinpoint. People with low self esteem are easily led by others, easily frustrated, often blame others for their shortcomings and avoid difficult situations. Low self esteem has been found to be associated with a series of self-defeating attitudes including involvement in some risk behaviours and other delinquent acts. Such behaviours may include; abuse of drug, lesbianism, homosexuals, premarital sex. Indeed, low self esteem has been shown to be correlated with a number of negative outcomes such as depression (Stein, & Book, 2006). The behaviour amongst the young ones with low self esteem no doubt constitutes a problem not only to themselves but also to the school, peers, parents, government and society at large. Low self esteem tends to disrupt the achievement, interest and needs of such students and to create in them unworthy and unstable feelings that tend to prevent them from expressing themselves, unable to defend their rights and stand up in matters that concern them. Low self-esteem can lessen a student's desire to learn and to focus, as well as the willingness to take risks.

Low self esteem is having a generally negative overall opinion of oneself, judging or evaluating oneself negatively, and placing a general negative value on oneself. Rosenberg and Owen (2001) described persons with low self esteem as people who are troubled by failure and who tended to exaggerate events and are generally negative in outlook. Such people they said often interpret non critical comments as critical; they experience social anxiety and have low levels of interpersonal confidence. These in turn make social interaction with others difficult as

they feel awkward, shy, conspicuous, and unable to adequately express them when interacting with others.

Low self esteem is a thinking disorder in which the individual views himself/herself as inadequate, unlovable, and incompetent. Once formed, this negative view permeates every thought, producing faulty assumptions and ongoing self-defeating behaviours such as; bullying, smoking, drinking, or disordered eating. Onyeizugbu (2003) noted that very many students struggle with low self esteem. He observed that some Nigerian students are characterized by heavy self criticism, tending to create a habitual state of dissatisfaction with themselves; suffer chronic indecision not because of lack of information but from an exaggerated fear of making a mistake. Others are excessively willing to please others out of fear of displeasing them, they show evidence of over-exploding frustration, depression, hostility, guilt, isolation and engage in crime, violence and other destructive behaviours. They exhibit these to compensate for their flaws. These negative characteristics may be related to the lack of encouragement or positive reinforcement from significant adults especially parents and peers.

Since low self esteem is detriment to students' wholesome development and good academic achievement, there is great need that those students who struggle with low self esteem be fished out and be assisted by the school, specifically the counsellor, to manage such inhibiting attitudes such as; shyness, timidity or debilitating feelings so their self confidence can be enhanced; which in turn will enable them cope with life challenges better. One of such method which has been shown in literature to be effective in helping people to control or manage their shyness, timidity and inability to express their emotions or demand for their rights is "assertiveness training".

Assertiveness training programs have been designed to improve individuals' assertive beliefs and behaviours and the results have shown increased self confidence and better social relationships among trainees (students) (Wesley and Mattaini, 2008). Corey (2009) had explained that assertiveness training is based on principles of social learning theory and it incorporates mainly social training methods. The scholar explained further that assertiveness training is often conducted in groups using modeling, role play and rehearsal to practice new behaviour in the therapist office and then enact same in everyday life.

According to Moon (2009) there is a positive relationship between assertiveness and self esteem. Mahmoodi, Jannati, Shoroofi, Hayadari, and Jafari (2002) studied the effect of assertiveness on level of anxiety in students and concluded that reduction in the level of anxiety in experimental group before and after assertiveness training was meaningful in comparison to the control group. Also, Paezy, Shahraray, and Abdi (2010), signified the effectiveness of assertiveness training on welfare and academic achievement of high school girls. Of interest in the present study is the influence of gender and age as variables that affect peoples' self esteem. Gender is generally assumed to impact upon the growth, demonstration and manifestation of self-esteem. Several researchers studied self-esteem and gender among students and found that there is a significant difference in self-esteem between male and female students (SarAbadani,

2006). Where some studies have found that gender has a moderating effect on assertiveness training, others found no significant effect of gender on assertiveness training (Agbakwuru & Ugwueze, 2010)

The most common difference is that male tends to have higher levels of self esteem throughout teenage years. When it does drop, male self esteem will not drop as low as females, and similarly male positive feelings about self are likely to be much stronger than a female positive self esteem (Robins, Trzesniewski, Tracy, Gosling, & Potter, 2004). A key difference between the genders is the effect of puberty on the body. Adolescent females have greater dissatisfaction with their bodies than males. For many girls, the physical changes with early adolescence often coincide with significant drop in self esteem levels (this is also compounded by puberty occurring during the transition from primary school). For girls, the increased body fat and change in shape can have negative effect. Conversely, the increase in muscle and strength among boys can have a positive effect (Robins, et al, 2004). This implies that as human advance in age, the feeling of self is affected.

Age is also assumed to have great impact in the manifestation of self esteem. One of the most significant periods for increased rates of lower self esteem is the transition from one stage of education to the next. The most observable is the transition from primary to junior secondary. Research has shown that between the ages of 8 and 13, teens self esteem levels drop markedly with girls more so than boys (Rhodes, Roffman, Reddy & Fredriksen, 2004). Even though some researchers such as; Moon (2009) have tried to study on the use of assertiveness training as a behaviour modification technique, none of them investigated on the effect of assertiveness training on low self esteem among secondary school students in Enugu North Local Government Area. Thus, the desire by the present researcher to seek solution to the problem of low self esteem which appears to grip many schooling adolescents in Enugu North L.G.A. of Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

In Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, some secondary school students face adverse life situations. This appears to arise from lack of relationship that should have provided them with care, and support, love and trust. Could it be that they need encouragement, both within and outside their families? According to Osarenren, Ubangha and Oke (2008), study of self-esteem has become necessary because of the implications of high and low self-esteem on individuals. For instance, issues have been raised that youth restiveness, violent behaviour, hooliganism, gangsterism, poor academic performance are some of the problems associated with low self-esteem and are prevalent among adolescents in Nigerian secondary schools.

On the other hand, it is proven that people with low self-esteem are always hyper-vigilant, as they are constantly anxious and fearful of making mistakes and overtly anxious of the behaviour of others; they are rarely assertive, as they are often too fearful of upsetting others, to tell the truth, ask for what they want, or share their feelings. Instead, they become passive until their anger builds up at points for which they become aggressive, defensive, sarcastic, rude or

violent as it is the case with domestic, gang and teen violence. (Baumeister, Campbell, Krueger & Vohs, 2003) In other words, the existing conditions among these students necessitate that an interaction programme be conducted to assist them i.e. those with low self esteem to face life challenges squarely without fears. This study, therefore, was designed to find the effect of assertiveness training on students with low self esteem.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effect of assertiveness training in the management of low self esteem among secondary school students. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the pretest and post test mean scores of students with low self esteem who were treated with assertiveness training and compared to those subjected to conventional counselling training.
2. Determine the pretest and post test mean scores of male and female students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.
3. Determine the pretest and post test mean scores of junior and senior secondary students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.

Significance of the Study

The researcher believes that the findings of this study will contribute immensely to the advancement of knowledge on the effect of assertiveness training on low self esteem among students. The finding will be valuable to those students with low self esteem, parents, teachers, counsellors, future researchers and the society at large. This study will benefit students with low self esteem specifically because; through assertiveness training, the students will learn a complex set of social skills that will enable them engage in effective, confident, and mutually beneficial interactions with other people. When students become more assertive, they will become happier; feel better about themselves. This will enable them to be able to accomplish what they plan to do since they have developed social skills. They will be able to relate and respond better in the class to the teacher and peers, which in turn will lead to better academic success and development.

Parents of these students will benefit in this study. If at the end of the study the students become restructured in their manner, then the students will come out sound in their relationship. The parents will be happy to see their children confident and proud to interact freely. This will help to create a better bond between the parents and their children thereby building a happy home for the growth and progress of the child's self actualization. Among those to benefit from this study are the teachers, who incidentally are the implementers of curriculum at the school and class room levels. Teachers will find the result of this study beneficial through the school counsellor who carries out teacher's forum in school from time to time. Through this forum,

teachers will gain insight on how to handle cases involving students with low self esteem in the way and manner that would reduce their problems and enhance their level of interaction in class interactive activities thus, enhancing their school achievements.

More so, the findings of this study will be an eye opener to counsellors in general and school counsellors in particular on the application and usefulness of assertiveness training. The findings will expose counsellors to understand that assertive training is a broad approach that can also be applied to enhance the self esteem of students and by extension improve their achievement. The study will be beneficial to future researchers who are investigating on related problems. The study will hopefully be a source of literature the future researchers will require to make meaningful research work. The findings of this work will also help them have an insight of the contemporary issues facing secondary school students. The society at large will definitely benefit from the findings of the study in the sense that, when the students of low self esteem can manage it effectively through assertiveness training, and can experience a reasonable level of assertiveness then, a healthy sense of self determination and respect for others are ultimately achieved. Such a balance helps each person work well with others, and makes appropriate decisions, thereby avoiding those anti-social behaviours that are harmful to the society. By and large, creating a suitable atmosphere for an all round growth and development for the generality of people.

Scope of the Study

The study was delimited to the effects of assertiveness training on low self esteem among secondary school students in Enugu North LGA, of Enugu State. The study was delimited to the co- educational schools in Enugu North L.G.A. The independent variable was assertiveness training which will be used to enhance students with low self esteem which is the dependent variable. The study was focused on how to use assertiveness training on low self esteem among all students in the identified school.

Research Questions

This study was guided with the following research questions;

1. What are the pretests and post test mean scores of students with low self esteem that was exposed to assertiveness training and those treated with conventional counselling training?
2. What are the pretests and post test mean scores of male and female students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training?
3. What are the pretests and post test mean scores of junior and senior secondary students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance;

1. There is no significant difference between the post test mean scores of students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training and those treated with conventional counselling training.
2. There is no significant difference between the post test mean scores of male and female students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.
3. There is no significant difference between the post test mean scores of junior and senior secondary students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.

Review of related Literature

Low Self Esteem

Rosenberg and Owen (2001) offer the following description of low self esteem people based on empirical research, that people with low self esteem are more troubled by failure and tend to exaggerative events as being negative. For example, they often interpret non critical comments as critical. Further, they said, such people are more likely to experience social anxiety and low levels of interpersonal confidence, which in turn makes social interaction with others difficult as they feel awkward, shy, conspicuous, and unable to adequately express oneself when interacting with others. According to Barnow, Lucht, & Freyberger (2005), children with low self esteem have a difficult time dealing with problems, they are overly self critical, and can become passive, withdrawn, and depressed. They may hesitate to try new things, may speak negatively about themselves, are easily frustrated, and often see temporary problem as permanent conditions. They are pessimistic about themselves and their life (Basmeister, Campbell, Krueger & Vohs, 2003). Furthermore, they concluded, low self esteem individuals tend to be pessimistic towards people and groups within the society. Low self esteem can therefore be seen as a feeling of unworthiness, and incompetence. Low self esteem is a debilitating condition that keeps individuals from realizing their full potentials. Low self esteem can be viewed as one's inability to accept oneself; one's tendency to live unhappily in accordance with principles which he does not understand but values, because not to value these principles would introduce the individual to a reality which, though he senses its existence and its rightness, he fears acknowledging.

Studies on Low Self Esteem

Signs of Self Esteem are: Having respect for oneself and others, being lovable and likable, being confident, and caring about oneself, creating a loving, healthy relationship, being a good friend to oneself and others, accepting oneself as one is (www.PRPonline.net)

4. **Some signs of low self-esteem:** Negative view of life, Perfectionist attitude, mistrusting others – even those who show signs of affection, blaming behavior, Fear of taking risks,

Feelings of being unloved and unlovable, Dependence – letting others make decisions, Fear of being ridiculed ([www.PRP online.net](http://www.PRP.online.net))

5. Characteristics of Low Self Esteem

6. Children with low self esteem withdraw rather than attempt a task because they are uncertain about their own abilities. They tend to be quiet and passive (Coopersmith, 1967). Because such children expect to fail, they do not try very hard and indeed often do not succeed. Children with low self esteem are easily led by others, easily frustrated, often blame others for their shortcomings and avoid difficult situations (Güloğlu, 1999). Children with a negative self worth, experience feelings of inadequacy and incompetence and fear rejection (Openshaw, 1978). They also are less likely to be objective about their capacities. They focus on their deficiencies, weaknesses and negative qualities (Kostelnik, 1988). Such children have little hope of influencing others. Consequently, they hesitate to express their opinions, lack independence and tend to feel isolated or alone (Coopersmith, 1967). Some changes occur as students mature. From about 4th grade on, self esteem tends to increase. One exception is the transition from elementary to junior high school. Until students adjust to the new demands of junior high schedules and workload, they may experience a decrease in self esteem. With growing competence and independence in adolescence, growth in self esteem resumes (Woolfolk, 1993).
7. Powel (2001) noted that there are people whose self esteem are below the expected for one to cope with life challenges. Individuals with low self esteem typically focus on trying to prove themselves or impress others. They tend to use other to gain. Some act with ignorance or contempt towards others. They generally lack confidence in themselves and often have doubts about their worth and acceptability and hence are reluctant to take risks. They often do not take responsibility of their failures; rather they attribute it to somebody else.
8. Low self esteem has a link to anti-social/maladaptive behaviours as, violence, alcoholism, rape, school dropout, teenage pregnancy, low academic achievement etc. low self esteem students tend to rely on coping strategies that are counterproductive as; bullying, quitting, avoiding and cheating.(Rotheram, Bickford, & Milburn. 2001). They noted that although some children display some of these behaviours at times, low self esteem are indicated when these behaviours appear regularly.

Causes and Consequences of Low Self Esteem

Low self esteem has no single factor that determines it; rather it develops from some factors such as family, environment and belief. Low self esteem is among the biggest deterrent to participation in educational activities, Anthony, Wood & Holmes (2004). Branden (2000) believed that the process of development of self esteem begins in childhood but solidifies and gain momentum

during the turbulent years of adolescences. Other researchers on low self esteem have believed that parents' child relationship can generate psychological disorder such as anxiety, identity confusion and conduct disorder (Dwairy, 2006). Background including socialization within the family play a very crucial role in the development of low self esteem and that family influence has been viewed as major factor, especially parenting style, physical abuse, family economic status, demographic factors, as they are related to low self esteem. Also, low self esteem can come to play in homes where parents do not provide adequately for the need of their children, attitude of some parents having favorites child amongst siblings, and the use of authoritarian or lesser faire parenting styles during early childhood and adolescence (McCabe & Timmins, 2006, Dwary, 2006).

Negative experience is said to be a predictors of low self esteem. Researchers' show that primary reason juvenile girls run away from home and go into prostitution is because of negative identity development as a result of negative experience they encountered during childhood. The development of low self has been consistently linked to early child experiences in form of negligence, abuse (physical), and ill treatment including lack of supports. Low self esteem can result in a lot of diminishing self-appreciation, creating self-defeating attitudes, vulnerability, social problems or risk behaviours, Joel and John (2006). Again Crocker & Pack (2004) similarly noted that a child that is abused physically or otherwise as well as not being shown affection and loves feeling abandoned, being punched, beaten, raped or molested during childhood may develop low self esteem. Crocker et al believes that such treatment from the environment follows the child to adulthood and definitely have negative impact on different aspects of the child's life leading to serious maladjustment and even escapism. Lacking trust in themselves, they become unable to handle daily problems which in turn reduce their ability to achieve maximum potentials.

Edwards, C. (2005) found a correlation between delinquency and low self esteem. He found that as programme were implanted to raise the level of self esteem, the incidence of delinquent behaviour in school declined. It is common to observe in some school where students who are punished for an offence resort to violence, damaging school property and beating up younger ones and even their teachers for retaliation. Poor self image is noted to be a product of low self esteem. It makes individuals develop compensation of inferiority complex, inactivity, apathy, boredom, depression and tend to escape mechanism and these lead them to engage in violence, cultism and even suicide (Ellis and Hartley, 2005).

Empirical Studies

Agbakwuru, and Ugwueze (2010), carried out a study on 'Effect of Assertiveness Training on Resilience among Early-Adolescents' in PortHarcourt, Nigeria. Pre-test post test experimental and control group design was used with some observation also made. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of assertiveness training on early-adolescents' improvement of

resilience. The training which consisted of 10 sessions of 50 minutes each was conducted at Army Day Secondary School in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. A total of 24 students aged 10-12 years were used for the study.

Randomization assignment was used to draw the 14 (8 male and 6 female) students to experimental and 10 (male and female) student to control groups. Researcher made early-adolescents' resilience scale (P.R.S) were used as instruments. Experts in the field of Guidance and Counselling validated the instruments for both pre-test and post-test. A test retest was employed at interval of two weeks to test for the reliability co-efficient of the instrument; Spearman's product moment correlation method was used to test the result. The correlated coefficients of early-adolescents' resilience scale = 0.84.

The summary of the research questions and hypothesis answered showed that there was positive effect of assertiveness training on improvement of resilience on respondents. The assertiveness training showed more improvement on resilience of the girls than that of the boys. From the statistical analysis, they concluded that the assertive training has been able to improve the level of resilience on the experimental group. This result shows that both the male and female students were affected equally by the assertiveness training. There were higher scores from the experimental group and for that it was attributed to the effect of assertive training on them. The observation carried out by the researcher and the teachers has a positive outcome. Recommendation was made for the need of counselling units in schools.

The study is relevant to the present study because, it worked on adolescents. It considered age and gender as variables and used pre-test post -test experimental and control group as its design. Also the study used assertiveness training as a treatment method. The study differs from the present study in that the assertiveness training was on resilience early adolescents. Osarenren & Ajaero (2013) examined the effects of two treatment methods on the self esteem and family Relationships of victims of sibling maltreatment among Junior Secondary School students (JSS2) in Lagos, Nigeria. Descriptive survey and Quasi- experimental pretest, post test control group research methodology were adopted for this study. A total of 180 (90 males and 90 females) junior secondary two served as participants for the experiments. The participants were selected after an initial survey of 300 junior secondary students. The students who scored 100 and above in Sibling Abuse Interview Schedule and 30 and above in Psychosocial Symptom Checklist were among those sampled for the experiments.

The experiment entailed teaching five lessons of Cognitive Restructuring and Assertiveness Training that spanned for five weeks. Each lesson lasted for 60 minutes per week .The participants in the three groups completed the assessment measures administered one week before the treatment and one week after the treatment. The three schools represented the three treatment groups. Two research hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The two instruments used to collect data were namely Self Esteem Rating Scale (SRS) and Index of Family Relations (IFL).

The data generated were analyzed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and Fisher's protected t- test. The findings revealed that Cognitive Restructuring and Assertiveness Training were effective in improving the self Esteem and Family Relationships of JSS2 students abused by sibling. Based on the findings it is concluded that the treatment method helped the participants in reducing the risk of psychological problems associated with Sibling maltreatment. The findings from this study are important for parent, counsellors, psychologists and all those working in the area of family and psychological violence. Furthermore, the findings bring to the fore empirical evidence of the debilitating effects of sibling maltreatment and some appropriate intervention strategies for handling same. The study is related the present study in that it used assertiveness training as a treatment model. The study also included gender as variable. The study differs with the present study in that it focused on a particular class of students (JSS2), while the present study is dealing with secondary students. Adile (2013) carried out a study on 'The Effect of an Assertiveness Training on the Assertiveness and Self Esteem Level of 5th Grade Children' in Ankara, Asia. The experimental design was used in which 2 groups were compared on pre test and post test measures by using Assertiveness Inventory and Coopersmith Self Esteem Inventory. This study aimed at developing an assertiveness program for 5th grade elementary school pupils and has the purpose of exploring the effects on children's level of assertiveness and self esteem. The participants of the study were from Ankara University Education Development Foundation Primary School, Asia. Twenty four pupils participated in the study. Moreover, observations of teachers were collected through the record sheets. The experimental group was given 8 week training. In order to explore the effects of assertiveness training on assertiveness levels of the children independent samples t test was used. The results revealed that there were significant differences between the two groups based on assertiveness scores. In order to explore the effects of assertiveness training on self esteem levels of children, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used. However, there were no significant differences found on self esteem scores between the two groups. On the other hand, according to the observations by the teachers, it could be stated that the training contributed positively to the children's self esteem. The study is relevant to the present study in that both are on self esteem, and also used ANCOVA in testing hypothesis. The studies differ in that the present study is specifically on low self esteem secondary school students.

Makinde and Akinteye (2013) investigated the effects of Mentoring and Assertiveness Training on Adolescents' self-esteem in Lagos State secondary schools. Descriptive survey and quasi-experimental design using the pre-test post-test control group design were adopted for the study. A total of 96 adolescents (48males and 48 females) drawn from three public schools randomly selected from three Education Districts in Lagos State constituted the final sample. The dependent variables for this study were self-worth and gender. Two instruments used to generate data for the study were: Adolescents' Personal Data Questionnaire (APDQ) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSE). Two research questions were raised and two corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The two hypotheses were tested using the one-

way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 levels of significance. Hypotheses 1 was rejected while hypothesis 2 was accepted.

The findings revealed that mentoring and assertiveness training were efficacious in raising adolescents' self-esteem. The study also found that the significant effect of mentoring and assertiveness training on adolescents' self-esteem was not due to gender. In the light of these findings, a number of recommendations were made, one of which is that teachers and schools' management should promote peer-mentoring programme in schools because of the numerous advantages it has over traditional mentoring. The study is relevant to the present study in that both are on self esteem of secondary students, using both male and female. The studies used ANCOVA in testing hypothesis. The studies differ in that the present study is specifically on low self esteem students.

Study on Low Self Esteem

A study carried out by Brent, Robins, Trzesniewski, Moffitt, and Caspi (2005) on "Low Self-Esteem Is Related to Aggression, Anti social Behaviour, and Delinquency" The research explored the controversial link between global self-esteem and externalizing problems such as aggression, antisocial behavior, and delinquency. The study investigated the relation between self-reports and teacher rating so f self-esteem and self-reports of delinquency in a sample of 11- and 14-year-olds. The sample included 292 (78% response rate) 11- and 14-yearoldparticipants (mean age = 12.66 years, SD = 1.57; 55%female; 56.5% European American, 4.8% Asian American or Pacific Islander, 20.5% Hispanic American, 9.2% African American, and 9.0% "other" or not reported) from two schools in northern California. Self-esteem was measured with the 10-item Rosenberg (1965) Self Esteem Scale (RSES; $\alpha = .81$) and the 6-item Global sub scale of the Harter (1985) Self-Perception Profile for Children (SPPC; $\alpha = .75$). Teachers completed a modified teacher version of the SPPC ($\alpha = .88$). Self-esteem was consistently negatively correlated with delinquency, regardless of whether self-esteem was assessed by the RSE ($r = -.35$), the self-report version of the SPPC ($r = -.39$), or the teacher version of the SPPC ($r = -.29$; all $ps < .05$). To explore these effects further, the self-esteem scores of individuals who reported at least one delinquent act (76% of the sample) was compared with those who reported no delinquent acts.

The delinquent group had lower self-esteem than the non delinquent group on all three self-esteem measures (Cohen's $d = 0.48, 0.63, \text{ and } 0.35$ for the RSE, self report SPPC, and teacher SPPC, respectively; all $ps < .05$). The study is related to the present study in that they are both on low self esteem and used self esteem rating instrument for data collection. Just like the present study, the study emphasized on adolescent age bracket. They differ in that the present study seeks to find the effect of assertiveness training on low self esteem students, the reviewed study is comparing teachers and students report on students self esteem based on delinquent and non delinquent group.

A study on 'improving the Performance of Low Self-Esteem Individuals: An Attribution Approach' was conducted by Joel and John (2006), in Arizona, United States. A total of 168 (97 female and 71 male) introductory ps at SUNY College at Brockport received course credit for completing the study. All subjects were randomly assigned to their experimental treatment. In the external (N= 41) and internal (N= 43) conditions the experimenter called subjects' attention to a bogus performance chart that had been placed on the wall in front of them. The chart described how well 60 "previous participants" had performed. In the external condition, subjects were informed that the task was very difficult, as 35 of the other participants failed to solve a single concept, 22 solved one or two, and only 3 solved all three. In the internal condition, subjects were led to believe that the task was relatively easy, as 35 of the previous subjects had solved all three concepts, 22 solved one or two, and only three solved none. Psychology students. Thus, it was expected that subjects, on encountering failure, would attribute it more to task characteristics (and /or less to self-aspects) in the external than in the internal condition. In the no information (N= 42) condition, subjects were given no feedback about the performance of other subjects. Once subjects had begun working on the task the experimenter made comments designed to buttress the attribution manipulation. In between concept formation trials one and two, the experimenter casually mentioned in the external (internal) condition: "Most people say they found the next concept to be harder (easier) than this one." In between trials two and three the experimenters aid: "Most everyone says this next one is even more difficult (easier) to identify." No such information was provided in the 'no' information condition.

The three behavioral dependent variables were: (1) number of anagrams solved, (2) mean time spent working on each anagram, and (3) mean time spent working only on those anagrams that had been solved. The first measure was determined by counting the number of anagrams (out of 20) that subjects solved within the 90-second limit. For the second measure the mean length of time each subject used to work on all 20 anagrams was recorded. (A score of 90 seconds was assigned to all trials in which the subject did not solve the anagram). The third measure was determined by computing the mean time spent only on those anagrams that subjects correctly solved. Two statistical analyses were conducted on each measure. In each instance a two-factor (self-esteem attribution) un-weighted-means analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed.

In order to provide a more powerful test of the effects of the self-esteem variables, only the data from those individuals who scored in the upper or lower thirds of the distributions were employed. In one analysis the self-esteem in dependent variable was determined by the individual's score on the depression measure, and in the other analysis it was determined by the Self-esteem score. The data from 112 (out of the 168) subjects were used in each analysis, although it was not necessarily the case that the identical subjects were used in the depression and Self-esteem analyses. In sum, the attribution results(particularly in the depression analyses) provided evidence that the subject's failure was seen as due more to the difficulty of the task in the external than in the other two conditions. This work is related to the present study for it investigated on low self esteem. It also used male and female students as subjects of experiment. The present study differs in that it has training approach on identified low self esteem student.

Summary of Review of Related Literature

The study reviewed some literature. Specifically, the study was conducted under these headings; concept of assertive training, concept of management, concept of self esteem, concept of low self esteem ,theoretical frame work, theoretical studies and empirical studies on assertiveness training, self esteem and low self esteem. This theory was discussed on assertiveness training; Social Learning Theory of Bandura (1971), while these theories were discussed as they relate to low self esteem; Theory of inferiority complex of Adler (1920) and Rogers Humanistic theory of (1902-1987). The researcher found out in most of the reviewed literature on empirical and theoretical studies, how effective assertiveness training is in modifying antisocial and maladaptive behaviours among adolescents. Low self esteem which is seen as one which can endanger students in committing such antisocial behaviours can be managed and controlled through assertiveness training of students. Low self esteem has been enhanced with some proven interventions in some studies including the use of assertiveness training, but little or no research has been carried out on effect of assertiveness training on low self esteem among secondary school students in Enugu North Local Government Area, Enugu State. This study has been designed to fill the existing gap.

METHOD

Research Design

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. Harrington and Harington (2006) described a quasi-experimental design as one that determines the effect of a treatment paradigm on a non-randomized sample. This study made use of a pre-test, post-test two groups, one experimental and one control non-randomized non- equivalent group and used an intact class. In notation form, the design can be depicted as follows;

Notational Representation of the Experimental Design

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
Experimental Group (1)	O1	X	O2
Control Group (2)	O1	-	O2

O = Pre-test/Post-test

X = Treatment

- = No Treatment

-

Area of the Study

The study was carried out at Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, in the eastern part of Nigeria. Enugu North is one of the seventeen Local Government Areas in Enugu State. Enugu North is situated at the centre of Enugu State. Enugu State is situated in inland south eastern Nigeria; Enugu state covers 7,161 square kilometers. It shares the same boundaries with Anambra State on the West, Abia State on the South, Kogi on the North while Benue and Ebonyi on the East, and Imo State on the South. It is an urban area, with many dwellers from all parts of the country and beyond. It is a semi-commercial area with a popular central market known as Ogbete market, Enugu. Enugu North has many schools (primary, secondary and tertiary, both government and private owned). There are a lot of commercial banks, transport companies and manufacturing industries at the area. A good percentage of the dwellers are civil servants, bankers, lawyers, politicians, traders and students. The researcher chose this area of study because; the researcher has observed and has also come in contact with some of these students. The researcher has actually noticed that some of these students are afraid of facing life challenges; they seem not to know what they want in life. Sometimes they lack care, support and encouragement from significant others as; parents, teachers in their lives thereby, resulting in the feelings of low self esteem. There are nine governments owned secondary schools in Enugu North, one boys' secondary school, four girls' secondary schools and four co-educational schools respectively. This statistic was obtained from PPSMB Headquarters, Enugu 2014/2015 record.

Population of the Study

The population for the study comprised all the 508 tested and identified low self esteem junior and senior secondary school students from the four coeducational schools in Enugu North L.G.A. Enugu State, through a pretest administration of 'Hare Self Esteem Scale' (HSS). This instrument was interpreted with the Nigerian norms of mean score of 87.70 as provided by (Anumba, 1995), which means that client who scored below 87.70 was regarded as having low self esteem, while scores above were high self esteem.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size was made up 114 junior and senior secondary school students. This number comprised all the low self esteem students from two co-educational schools. These two co-educational schools were purposively selected from the four co-educational schools administered (pre-test) with Hare Self Esteem Scale (HSS) as prepared by Anumba (1995). The distribution of the low self esteem students selected for the study is shown.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a self esteem inventory developed by B.R. Hare (1985), and adapted by Anumba (1995). The instrument is titled; Hare Self Esteem Scale. It was used to select those with low self esteem to be placed in treatment and control group (i.e. Pre-test) and also to evaluate the effect of the treatment (i.e. Post-test). The Scale consists of 30 item rating

scale. The 30 item inventory is designed to assess the influence of three factors; the peer group, school and the home on self esteem of children in primary and secondary schools. The items were presented on a 4 point rating scale, ranging from strongly disagree (1point) to strongly agree (4 point) . This determined the respondents' level of agreement or disagreement to an item statement.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was an already validated instrument developed by Hare (1985) and adapted by Anumba (1993) for Nigerian use, and adopted by the researcher. Validity co-efficient were obtained by correlating HSS with other tests. Hare (1985) obtained a concurrent coefficient of .83 with Rosenberg self esteem Scale developed by Rosenberg (1979) while Anumba obtained a divergent coefficient of .62 in an index of peer relation by Hudson, W.W., Nurius, P.S., J.G. and Newsome (1986).

Reliability of the Instrument

Hare (1979) reported a test-retest reliability coefficient of .74 in an interval of three months.

Method of Data Collection

The data was collected for the study through the following means:

Training of the Research Assistants

The researcher gave a one week training of two meetings (30 minutes each) to the school counsellors of the two schools used. They were guided on how the inventory was to be distributed and collected. The researcher also gave an over view of the sessions that were involved in the treatment. The researcher engaged the guidance counsellors in the steps and procedures involved in assertiveness training. This was to get them acquainted with the knowledge of assertiveness training and made the study easy and stress free. It also helped them get equipped in order to get the students interested in the training proper.

Experimental Procedure

The data for the study was collected by the researcher with the help of school counsellor (research assistant) of each of the schools to be used for the study. The instrument by B.R Hare, 'Hare Self Esteem Scale' was administered to the students as a pre-test. This served as a diagnostic test and helped to identify those with low self esteem that were placed in experimental and control group respectively, after which assertiveness training treatment was administered to the experimental group and conventional counselling was given to the control group. The sessions for the treatment lasted for 60 minutes twice a week for six weeks, a total of 12 sessions (See Appendix D, Pg: 77). The assertiveness training program for the students was captioned; "You have right! Others have right". The language of the assertiveness training program was prepared in a simple and clear form and also some adolescent languages can be cheeped as the training progresses. This was to enable the students feel relaxed and put their in the training. The same instrument

was reshuffled by the researcher together with the counsellor (research assistant) to further be administered to both experimental and control groups as post-test. This was to determine the effect of the treatment after a specified period of six weeks of assertiveness training programme. The researcher collected the inventory papers from the students for proper scoring.

Control of Extraneous Variables

In an experimental work as this, there is a possibility that some variable may try to hamper the success of the study. In order to avoid such therefore, the researcher made effort to ensure the control of these variables;

Hawthorne Effect

The researcher assumed that the students might not want to disclose their real behaviour if they notice that they would be used for an experiment. The researcher in view of avoiding this used the school counsellor (research assistant) who the students are already familiar with, especially in terms of the counsellor's counselling approach method of teaching in their usual group guidance activities. This idea made the students feel relaxed and responded to the inventory that were distributed to them by the counsellor with relevant instructions that guided the students.

Clients Interaction with regard to age:

The junior and senior secondary students of the same treatment were treated separately during the treatment to avoid distractions, such as bullying of the junior ones.

Method of Data Analysis

There was direct scoring and reverse scoring of the items. Direct scoring involved item numbers; 1,3,5,7,9,11,13,15,17,19,22,24,26,28,&30, while reverse scoring involved item numbers; 2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18,20,23,25,27,29. Both direct and reverse scores were added to obtain the overall score of a client.

The data which was obtained through the self esteem inventory was compiled, analyzed and presented in a tabular form using the mean score of 87.70, as provided by (Anumba, 1995) for Nigerian norms; which means that any score below 87.70 was regarded as having low self esteem, while scores above are high self esteem. Arithmetic mean was used to answer research questions, while Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the null hypotheses for the study which enabled the researcher test significant differences between the variables.

Research Question 1

What are the pretest and posttest mean scores of students with low self esteem that was exposed to assertiveness training and those treated with conventional counselling training?

Table 1: pretest and posttest mean scores of students with low self esteem treated with assertiveness training and those treated with conventional counselling training

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Gained Mean	Remark
Assert. Training	57	50.33	87.72	37.39	Not Effective
Control Group	57	52.46	83.33	30.87	

Table 1 indicates that the students with assertiveness training had pretest mean score of 50.33 and posttest mean score of 87.72 with gained mean of 37.39 in their low self esteem, while the students with conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 52.46 and post test mean score of 83.33 with gained mean of 30.87. Therefore, assertiveness training is slightly effective on low self esteem students.

Research Question 2

What are the pretest and posttest mean scores of male and female students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training?

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest mean scores of male and female students with low self esteem treated with assertiveness training

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Gained Mean	Remark
Male	17	52.47	90.94	38.47	slight difference
Female	40	49.43	86.35	36.92	

Table 2 shows that male students treated with assertiveness training had pretest mean score of 52.47 and posttest mean score of 90.94 with gained mean of 38.47 in their low self esteem, while the female students treated with assertiveness training had pretest mean score of 49.43 and posttest mean score of 86.35 with gained mean of 36.92. Therefore, assertiveness training is slightly effective on male students than the female students.

Research Question 3

What are the pretest and posttest mean scores of junior and senior secondary school students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training?

Table 3: Pretest and Posttest mean scores of junior and senior students with low self esteem treated with assertiveness training

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Gained Mean	Remark
Junior	33	50.73	90.45	39.72	slight difference
Senior	24	49.79	83.96	34.17	

Table 3 reveals that the junior students treated with assertiveness training had pretest mean score of 50.73 and posttest mean score of 90.45 with gained mean of 39.72 in their low self esteem, while the senior students treated with assertiveness training had pretest mean score of 49.79 and posttest mean score of 83.96 with gained mean 34.17. Therefore, assertiveness training is slightly effective on junior students than the senior students.

Testing the Null Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference in the posttest mean scores of students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training and those treated with conventional counselling training.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the posttest self esteem mean scores of students treated with assertiveness training and those treated with conventional counselling training

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	Remark
Corrected Model	1857.428	2	928.714			
Intercept	42077.664	1	42077.664			
HSS1	1309.183	1	1309.183			
Treatment Models	374.249	1	374.249	2.25	3.99	NS
Error	18500.993	111	166.676			
Total	854240.000	114				
Corrected Total	20358.421	113				

In Table 4 it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1 df numerator and 113 df denominator, the calculated F 2.25 is less than the critical F 3.99. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is accepted. So, the slight effect of assertiveness training on secondary school students' with low self esteem is not significant when compared with those in the control group.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the posttest mean scores of male and female students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.

Table 5: ANCOVA on the posttest mean scores of low self esteem male and female students treated with assertiveness training.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	Remark
Corrected Model	1357.351	4	339.338			
Intercept	13479.829	1	13479.829			
HSS1	404.861	1	404.861			
Gender	411.953	1	411.953	2.92	4.02	NS
Error	7344.158	52	141.234			
Total	447298.000	57				
Corrected Total	20358.421	56				

Table 5 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 56df denominator, the calculated F 2.92 is less than the critical F 4.02. Therefore, the second null hypotheses are accepted. So, the effect of assertiveness training on male than female secondary school students with low self esteem is not significant.

Hypotheses 3

There is no significant difference between the posttest mean scores of junior and senior secondary students with low self esteem who were exposed to assertiveness training.

Table 6: ANCOVA on the posttest mean scores of junior and senior students treated with assertiveness training.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	Remark
Corrected Model	1357.351	4	339.338			
Intercept	13479.829	1	13479.829			
HSS1	404.861	1	404.861			
Age	370.202	1	370.202	2.621	4.02	NS
Error	7344.158	52	141.234			
Total	447298.000	57				
Corrected Total	8701.509	56				

Table 6 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 56df denominator, the calculated F 2.62 is less than the critical F 4.02. Therefore, the third null hypothesis is accepted. So, the effect of assertiveness training on junior than senior secondary school students with low self esteem is not significant.

Summary of the Findings

From the analysis, the following findings were made:

1. Assertiveness training was slightly effective on low self esteem secondary school students.
2. Assertiveness training was slightly effective on male than the female student with low self esteem.
3. Assertiveness training was slightly effective on junior than senior secondary school students with low self esteem
4. The slight effect of assertiveness training on low self esteem students treated with assertiveness training is not significant when compared with those who received conventional counselling training.
5. The slight effect of assertiveness training on male than female secondary school students with low self esteem is not significant.
6. The slight effect of assertiveness training on junior than senior secondary school students with low self esteem is not significant.

Discussion, Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, the discussions of the findings, implications, limitations, recommendations and conclusions are presented. The discussion of the findings is based on the purposes of the study. Consequent upon findings, implications, recommendations and suggestions were made for further studies.

Discussion of the Findings

Students with low Self Esteem Treated with Assertiveness Training and Conventional Counselling

The result of the study shows that low self esteem secondary school students in the experimental group who were treated with assertiveness training performed slightly better after the training than those in the control group who received conventional counselling training. The study indicates that the mean gain score from pretest to posttest on those exposed to assertiveness training was slightly above those who received conventional counselling. Data in Table 4 showed that although there was slight effect of assertiveness training on the low self esteem secondary students, the effect has no significant.

This finding is in line with a study carried out by Gulsah (2013) Ankara, Asia On 'The Effect of an Assertiveness Training on the Assertiveness and Self Esteem Level of 5th Grade Children'. In the study, in order to explore the effects of assertiveness training on self esteem levels of children, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used. However, there were no significant differences found on self esteem scores between the two groups.

Male and Female Students with Low Self Esteem Treated with Assertiveness Training

The result showed that male low self esteem secondary school students exposed to assertiveness training had higher pretest and posttest mean score than the female low self esteem secondary school students. Data in Table 2 showed slight effect on gender, the male improved better than the female. However, the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for gender in table 5 showed there was no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female low self esteem students treated with assertiveness training. This finding goes with studies by several researchers on self-esteem and gender among students which found out that there is a significant difference in self-esteem between male and female students (SarAbadani, 2006). Where some studies have found that gender has a moderating effect on assertiveness training, others found no significant effect of gender on assertiveness training (Agbakwu, 2000).

Junior and Senior Students with Low Self Esteem Treated with Assertiveness Training

The result shows that the pretest and posttest mean scores of low self esteem junior secondary school students treated with assertiveness training were improved than the senior secondary school students with low self esteem who were treated with assertiveness training. Data in Table

3 revealed that assertiveness training gained more effect on the junior students than the senior students, although the effect of age has no significant effect as shown in table 6 of the analysis of the covariance (ANCOVA). This finding agrees with the study carried out by Osarenren & Ajaero (2013), which examined the effects of cognitive restructuring and assertiveness training on the self esteem among junior secondary students. The findings revealed that assertiveness training were effective in improving the self esteem of the junior secondary school students. Also, Age is assumed to have great impact in the manifestation of self esteem. One of the most significant periods for increased rates of lower self esteem is the transition from one stage of education to the next. The most observable is the transition from primary to junior secondary. Research has shown that between the ages of 8 and 13, teens self esteem levels drop markedly with girls more so than boys (Rhodes, Roffman, Reddy & Fredriksen, 2004).

Implication of the Study

The researcher expected that the use of assertiveness training on low self esteem among secondary school students in Enugu North L.G.A would be of immense significant, but this study revealed that assertiveness training when used on low self esteem students was statistically insignificant. Therefore, the possession of assertiveness training technique to a low extent by the counsellor educators, professional counsellors and counsellors in training in helping students with low self esteem implies that they are incompetent in taking care of their clients. More so, this research work has implication on the government through its agent; ministry of education. The counsellor educators, professional counsellor and counsellors in training need in-service training to enable them improve on their services to their clients. In-service training programmes such as seminars and workshops can be organized by the ministry of education on assertiveness training techniques for the counsellors. The counsellors on their own part can work on themselves to improve in their knowledge by reaching out to useful books on assertiveness training and making researches on its application on low self esteem among secondary school students.

Moreover, implications of this study also boils down to the Counselling Association of Nigeria (CASSON). This body should endeavor among other things to involve para-counsellors in attending conferences and other training avenues where they will be exposed to the knowledge of assertiveness training. Such training will help them to observe and identify students with low self esteem and also those who pretend to have low self esteem, who does not want to show their real identity. This is because, from the findings of this study, some of the participants pretend to have low self esteem, while some others pretend not to have, thereby making the study yield an insignificant result.

Conclusion

It is clear that assertiveness training is statistically insignificant. This means that counsellors need competences in the areas of assertiveness training, their counselling theories and their applications. Counselling as a helping profession therefore, requires that those who practice it be trained and retrained from time to time to enable them render help to individuals

such as low self esteem students in their interaction with peers, teachers, parents and other people in their life.

Recommendations

1. Counsellor Educators, professional counsellors and counsellors in training can improve their counselling techniques by attending conferences, seminars and workshops to get them grounded in areas assertiveness training to enable them have significant impact on low self esteem secondary school student when trained with assertiveness training.
2. Counsellors should at least once in every academic session organize seminar for parents to enlighten them on how to help their children especially those with low self esteem, to have new knowledge in assertive behaviour
3. The government through the ministry of education should provide scheme of work for these counsellors, give them in service training from time to time so as to enable them gain more new insight on assertive behaviour. This will enhance them better on how to curb the issue of low self esteem among secondary school students through the assertiveness training they will offer to the students.

References

- Agbakwuru, C. & Ugwueze, S. (2010). Effect of Assertiveness Training on Resilience Among Early-Adolescents. *European Scientific Journal* May edition vol. 8, No.10 ISSN: 1857 – 7881 (Print) e - ISSN 1857- 7431
- Adile G.S (2013). *The effect of an assertiveness training on the assertiveness and self esteem level of 5th grade children in Ankara, Asia*. An Unpublished Master Thesis submitted to the department of Educational Sciences, Middle East Technical University.
- Adler, A. (1938). *Social Interest: A challenge to mankind*. J. Linton and R. Vaughan (Trans.). London: Faber and Faber Ltd.
- Akert, M. Robin, Aronson, E., & Wilson, D.T. (2005). *"Social psychology"* (5th ed.). Pearson Education, Inc.
- Alberti, R. E., & Emmons, M. L. (2008). *Your perfect right: Assertiveness and equality in your life and relationships (9th ed.)*. Atascadero, CA: Impact Publishers.
- Anthony, D.B wood, JV & Holmes, JG (2007). Self esteem and the importance of acceptance for social decision-making. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 43 (3) 1331-1341.
- Anumba, A. C. (1995). *The influence of peer relations on self-esteem, assertiveness and ego-strength of adolescents*. Unpublished thesis submitted to the department of Psychology, University of Lagos.
- Baker, L.L. & Scarth, K. (2002). *Cognitive behavioural approach to treating children and adolescents with conduct disorder*. Children's Mental Health Ontario.
- Bandura, A. (1971). Psychotherapy based upon modeling principles. In A. Bergin and S. Garfield (Eds.), *Handbook of psychotherapy and behaviour change*. New York: Wiley.
- Barnow, S., Lucht, M., & Freyberger, H. (2005). Correlates of aggressive and delinquent conduct problems in adolescence. *Aggressive Behavior*, 31(1), 24–39.
- Baumeister, R. F., Campbell, J. D., Krueger, J. I., & Vohs, K. D. (2003). Does high self-esteem cause better performance, interpersonal success, happiness or healthier life-style? *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*,4(1), 1-44.
- Beck, A., Freeman, A., & Davis, D. (2004). *Cognitive therapy of personality disorders (2nd ed.)*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Bishop, S. (1997). *The complete guide to people skills*. Farnham: Gower Pub Co.
- Bishop, S. (2010). *Develop your assertiveness (2nd ed.)*. London: Kogan Page.
- Branden, N. (2000). *How to raise your self-esteem?* New York: Bantam Books.
- Brent, D., Kali, H. T., Richard, W. R., Terrie, E. M, & Avshalom, C. (2005). *Low self-esteem is related to aggression, antisocial behavior, and delinquency* Published by: Sage Publications, Inc. on behalf of the Association for Psychological Science Stable URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40064223>

- Canter, L., & Canter, M. (2001). *Assertive discipline: Positive behavior management for today's classroom*. Santa Monica, CA: Canter & Associates Inc.
- Christopher, A., Edwards, C., & Eppler, C. (2012). *School based group counseling*. Belmont, CA: Brooks-Cole.
- Coopersmith, S. (1967). *The antecedents of self esteem*. Princeton, N. J.: Princeton University Press.
- Corey, G (2009). *Theory and practice of counselling and psychotherapy* (8th edition) Thomson Brooks/Cole publishing Co.
- Crocker, J & Parks, L.E (2004). The costly pursuit of self esteem. *Psychological Bulletin*, 130,392-414.
- Dixie, G., & Bell, J. (2009). *The trainee primary teacher's handbook*. New York: Continuum.
- Dwairy, M (2006). Cultural sensitive education adapting self oriented assertiveness training to collective minorities. *Journal of Social Issues*, 60(2), 423-436.
- Edwards, C. (2005). *Classroom discipline and management*. New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Ellis, J & Hartley .C. (2005). *Managing and coordinating nursing care, (4th ed)*. Lippincott Williams and Wilkins Co. Philadelphia, New York, London pp 7-8, 136.
- Greenwald, A. G., & Farnham, S. D. (2000). Using the Implicit Association Test to measure self-esteem and self-concept. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 79, 1022–1038. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.7.6.1022
- Güloğlu, B. (1999). *The effect of a self-esteem enrichment programme on the self-esteem level of elementary school students*. Middle East Technical University, Ankara.
- Hare, B.R. (1965). *The Hare general and area specific(school, peer, and home) self-esteem scale*. New York The Free Press.
- Harrington, H. & Harrington, C. (2006). *Research and theory to reach all learners*. Retrieved on 15th June 2014 from: www.ideas.repec.org.
- Harter, S. (1985). *The self-perception profile for adolescents*. Unpublished manuscript, University of Denver, Denver, CO.
- Joel, B. & John, G. (2006). *Improving the Performance of Low Self-Esteem Individuals: An Attributional Approach* Published by: Academy of Managements table URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/255912> Accessed: 27-01-2016 10:13 UTC
- Kaufman, C., Raphael, L., & Espeland, P. (2000). *A teacher's guide to stick up for yourself: A 10-part course in self-esteem and assertiveness for kids*. Minneapolis, MN: Free Spirit Publishing Inc.
- Korobkova, T. A. (2000). Asertivnost' kak vid pedagogičeskoj komunikacii [Assertiveness as a kind of pedagogical communication]. In T. A. Korobkova (Ed.)
- Kostelnik, M. J. (1988). *Guiding children's social development*. New York: South Western.
- Lazarus, A. (1971). *Behavioural therapy and clinical problems: a critical overview annual review of behavioural therapy: theory and practice*, New York burner Mazel.

- Mahmoodi G, Jannati Y. Shoroofi SA. Hayadari, MA,& Jafari H, (2002). *Survey on the effect of assertive therapy on the amount of educational anxiety in students*. J. Mazandaran Uni Med Sci 2003, 37:39-45 (Persian).
- Makinde and Akinteye (2013). Effects of mentoring and assertiveness training on Adolescents' self-esteem. *International Journal of Social Science Studies* Vol. 2, No. 3; July 2014 ISSN 2324-8033 E-ISSN 2324-8041 Published by Red fame Publishing URL: <http://ijsss.redfame.com>
- McCabe, C., & Timmins, F. (2006). *Teaching assertiveness to undergraduate nursing students*. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 3(1), 30-42. Doi: 10.1016/S1471-5953(02)00079-3
- Miheykina, S. V. (2010). On the question of the relationship between aggressive and confident behavior in the psychological interpretation of the behavioural activity of the individual. Retrieved from <http://www.psyedu>
- Moon, J. (2009). *Achieving success through academic assertiveness: Real life strategies for today's higher education student* New York: Routledge.
- Nelson, A. (2003). Peer Mentoring. A Citizenship Entitlement at Tanfield School. *Pastoral CareInEducation* 21(4), 34 - 41.
- Nelsen, E. D. J., Duffy, R., Escobar, L., Nelsen, J., Ortolano, K., & Owen-Sohocki, D. (2001). *Positive discipline: A teacher's A-Z guide: Hundreds of solutions for every possible classroom*. New York.
- Okeke, B.A. (1997). *Techniques and Practicum in Guidance and Counselling*. Enugu: CPA and Gold Publishers.
- Okoli, C. E. (2002). *Techniques of behaviour modification*. Lagos: Behenu Press and Publishers.
- Olayinka, M. S., & Omoegun, O. M. (2001). *Principles and practice of guidance and counseling*. Lagos: Babsheriff Limited.
- Omoluabi P. F. (1997) *Hare Self Esteem Scale*. Manual Series Editor: PPC Consultant in Nigeria, University of Lagos, Nigeria.
- Onyeizugbu, E. U (2003). *Effects of gender, age and education on assertiveness in a Nigerian sample psycho women*, 27, 12 - 6.
- Openshaw, D. K. (1978). *The development of self esteem in the child: Model Theory versus parent-child interaction*. Brigham Young University, Utah.
- Osarenren, N., Ubangha, M. B., & Oke, T. D. (2008). Family characteristics as correlates of self esteem among young adults. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 4(1), 17-25.
- Osarenren, N. & Ajaero, I. (2003). Effects of two treatment methods on the self esteem and family Relationships of victims of sibling maltreatment among Junior Secondary School students. *Research Journal in Organizational Psychology & Educational Studies*, 2(3), 93 - 100 Rjopes© Emerging Academy Resources (2013) (ISSN: 2276-8475) www.emergingresource.org
- Paezy, M., Shahraray, M., & Abdi, B. (2010). Investigating the impact of assertiveness training on assertiveness, subjectivewell-being and academic achievement of Iranian female secondary students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 5, 1447-1450.

- Patseka, I. M. (2010). Preparation of primary school teachers to work on early prevention of deviant behavior (Abstract of doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from <http://www.dissercat.com/content/podgotovka-uchitelei-nachalnykh-klassov-k-rabote-po-rannei-profilaktike-deviantnogo>
- Powell, P.M. (2001). *Elementary education, personal adjustment and social achievement in a national sample of gifted adults in gifted children reaching their potentials*, edited by James Gallagher. Republished by Trillium Press.
- Rhodes, J., Roffman, J., Reddy, R., & Fredriksoen, K. (2004). Changes in self esteem during the middle school years: a latent growth curve study of individual and contextual influences. *Journal of School Psychology, 42* (1), 243-261.
- Robins, R.W., Trzesniewski, K.H., Tracy, J.L., Gosling, S.D., & Potter, J. (200). Global self-esteem across the lifespan. *Journal of Psychology and Aging, 17*(1), 423-434.
- Rogers, C. R. (1942). *Counseling and psychotherapy*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Rogers, C. (1959). A Theory of Therapy, Personality and Interpersonal Relationships as Developed in the Client-centered Framework. In S. Koch (Ed.), *Psychology: A Study of a Science, 3: Formulations of the Person and the Social Context*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Romek, V. G. (2003). Training of confidence in interpersonal relations. Retrieved from <http://www.klex.ru/809Psychological Thought2013>, (1), 3–26 doi:10.5964/psyct.v6i1.14
- Rosenberg, M. (1965). *Society and adolescent self-image*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University.
- Rosenberg, M and Owens TJ (2001). Low self esteem people. A collective Portrait in TJ Owens & Strykes & Goodonan (eds). *Extending self esteem theory and research* (pp-400-436) New York Cambridge Press. *Social psychology quarterly, 46*77-88.
- Rotheram M. J., Bickford, B., & Milburn, N. G. (2001). Implementing a classroom-based social skills training program in middle childhood. *Journal of Educational & Psychological Consultation, 12*(2), 91-112.
- Salter, A. (2002). *Conditioned reflex therapy: The classic book on assertiveness that began behavior therapy*. Gretna, LA: Wellness Institute.
- SarAbadani, T.L. (2006). *The relationship between academic achievement, self-esteem and gender with anxiety of computer among postgraduate students in the University of Tabeiyat Moallem Tehran*. University of Tabeiyat Moallem Theran. Iran.
- Savage, T., & Savage, M. (2010). *Successful classroom management and discipline: Teaching self-control and responsibility*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Smith, M. J. (1985). *When I say no, I feel guilty*. New York: Bantam Books.
- Smith, M. J. (2006). *Training of self-confidence: A Set of exercises to develop confidence*. Retrieved from <http://www.orator.biz/library/books/traning>
- Stein, S., & Book, H. (2006). *The EQ edge: Emotional intelligence and your success* (2nd ed.). Toronto, Ontario: Jossey-Bass.
- Stepanov, S. S. (2006). *Mify i tupiki pop-psihologii* [Myths and blind alleys of pop psychology]. Dubna: Feniks. Retrieved from <http://www.klex.ru/ash>

- Stephen P. Robbins & Philip L. (2007). *Training in interpersonal Skills, (4th ed)*., Pearson Education , Inc. Delhi.
- Ullrich, R., & Ullrich de Muynck, R. (1973). Standardisierung des Selbstsicherheitstrainings für Gruppen. In J.C. Brengelmann & W. Tunner (Eds.), *Behavior Therapy – Verhaltenstherapie* (pp. 252-260). München: Urban und Schwarzenberg.
- Wesley, J. M. and Mattaini, M. A (2008). Assertiveness Skills Education: <http://www.peacepower.info/modules/RespectAssert.pdf> Retrieved on 21/02/2010
- Woolfolk, A. E. (1993). *Educational psychology*. California: Allyn & Bacon.